

Addition Compounds of Organotin Halides—II. Adducts of Di-*n*-propyl tin dichloride with Amines

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Adducts of di-*n*-propyl tin dichloride with amines have been prepared and assignments for various modes of vibration are given. Molar conductance values of these adducts in nitrobenzene have shown that they are non-ionic in nature.

The chemistry of organotin halides has evoked much interest in the recent past and quite extensive investigations towards the structural aspects of organotin halides and their adducts, also have been carried out ¹⁻⁹.

An adduct of di-*n*-propyl tin dichloride with pyridine was reported as back as in 1911¹⁰, nothing has been reported about its structural aspect. In the present study, adducts of di-*n*-propyl tin dichloride (Pr_2SnCl_2) with quite a few amines have been prepared and characterised by measurement of their molar conductance values and infra red absorption frequencies.

EXPERIMENTAL

Di-*n*-propyl tin dichloride was prepared from tetrapropyl tin and tin tetrachloride as described by Kocheshkov¹¹. It was purified by crystallization from petroleum ether and distilled under vacuum to yield a crystalline needle like product with m.pt. 79-80°. The adducts were prepared by mixing the solutions of the bases and Pr_2SnCl_2 in suitable quantities in anhydrous petroleum ether at ice cold temperature. The solid products were filtered, washed with dry petroleum ether under anhydrous conditions, dried under vacuum and analysed for their tin and chlorine contents. The analytical data including m.pt., and molar conductances in nitrobenzene are given in Table 1.

Their Infra red absorption spectra have been studied in the region 4000-400 cm^{-1} as KBr discs on a Perkin Elmer 337 grating spectrophotometer. The far infra red studies between 400-250 cm^{-1} have also been carried out.

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TABLE I

Adducts of Di-n-propyl tin dichloride with bases

S.No.	Adducts	m.pt. °C	Molar conduc- tances at 25° cm ² .ohm ⁻¹ .mole ⁻¹	% of tin		% of Cl	
				Required	Found	Required	Found
1.	Pr ₂ SnCl ₂ .2 Pyridine	110—112	2.476	27.41	27.12	16.35	16.45
2.	Pr ₂ SnCl ₂ .2-β-Picoline	85—86	3.553	25.75	25.23	15.37	15.54
3.	Pr ₂ SnCl ₂ .2-γ-Picoline	124—125	4.624	25.75	25.35	15.37	15.24
4.	Pr ₂ SnCl ₂ .2.Isoquinoline	158—159	2.111	22.28	22.74	13.29	13.12
5.	Pr ₂ SnCl ₂ .2.Piperidine*	179—180	—	26.68	26.25	15.91	15.74
6.	Pr ₂ SnCl ₂ .x.Morpholine*†	181—182	—	—	—	—	—
7.	Pr ₂ SnCl ₂ .2.Aniline	83—84	3.237	25.75	26.14	15.35	15.49
8.	Pr ₂ SnCl ₂ .x.Benzylamine*†	253—255	—	—	—	—	—

* Solubility in nitrobenzene at 25° is too low.

† Stoichiometry not clear.

DISCUSSION

The spectra of adducts of amines with Lewis acids have been studied by a number of workers and various perturbations associated with the donation of electrons from nitrogen atom have been assigned by earlier workers¹²⁻¹⁶. On similar basis the structures of the present adducts have also been established.

Donation of the lone pair of electrons from nitrogen in pyridine¹⁴ and other tertiary bases has been reported to cause appreciable changes in the C = C and C = N frequencies. The observations in the present case are also similar (Table II).

TABLE II

*C = C and C = N frequencies
(cm⁻¹)*

Pyridine	1583	1572	1483	1439
(Py H) ⁺ Cl ⁻ (12)	1631	1603	1530	1481
Pr ₃ SnCl.Pyridine (9)	1625	1595	1510	1470
Pr ₂ SnCl ₂ .2.Pyridine	1600	1575	1490	1460
β-Picoline	1610	1587	1492	1458
β-Picolinium (16)	1625	1608	1550	1480
Pr ₃ SnCl.β-Picoline (9)	1600	1580	1495	1450
Pr ₂ SnCl ₂ .2-β-Picoline	1595	1580	1500	1460
γ-Picoline	1595	1556	1492	1435
γ-Picolinium (16)	1620	1600	1540	1480
Pr ₃ SnCl.γ-Picoline (9)	—	1600	1545	1495
Pr ₂ SnCl ₂ .2γ-Picoline	1630	1575	1515	1460
Isoquinoline	1630	1590	1500	1465
Isoquinolinium (16)	1650	1605	1560	1480
Pr ₃ SnCl.Isoquinoline (9)	1650	1625	—	1475
Pr ₂ SnCl ₂ .2-Isoquinoline	1620	1590	1550	1475

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Frequencies at 605 cm^{-1} and 405 cm^{-1} in case of pyridine, which have been reported to show an upward trend on co-ordination¹⁴, appear at 615 cm^{-1} and 425 cm^{-1} respectively in the present case.

N-H frequencies : In piperidine, morpholine, aniline and benzyl amine, co-ordination through nitrogen weakens the N-H bond. Simultaneously some additional hydrogen bonding between the hydrogen of the N-H and halogen of the Lewis acid is also expected and this renders the N-H bond still weaker. This is evident from Table III.

TABLE III
N-H frequencies
(cm^{-1})

	$\nu(\text{N-H})$	$\delta(\text{N-H})$	(H-N-C) deformations
Piperidine (12)	3291 m	1650 m	822 m
Pr_3SnCl .Piperidine(9)	3160 m	1580 s	847 s
Pr_2SnCl_2 .2-Piperidine	3150 m	1555 s	845 s
Morpholine	3340 s	1675 s	830 s
Morpholine-hydrochloride	—	1550 s	860 s
Pr_3SnCl .Morpholine(9)	3260 s	1550 s	855 s
Pr_2SnCl_2 .x.Morpholine	3270 m	1545 s	855 s
Aniline	3315 m	1610 s	
	3280 m		
Aniline-hydrochloride	—	1550 s	
Pr_3SnCl .Aniline(9)	—	1580 s	
Pr_2SnCl_2 .2.Aniline	—	1590 s	
Benzylamine	3330 m	1620 s	805 m?
	3250 m		
Benzylamine hydrochloride	—	1590 s	870 m?
Pr_3SnCl .Benzylamine (9)	—	1580 s	865 m?
Pr_2 . SnCl_2 .x.Benzylamine	—	1575 s	870 m?

Sn-C frequencies : Sn-C frequencies, although dependent upon the effective nuclear charge of the tin atom, are relatively insensitive to co-ordination of the tin atom.

In the spectrum of di-*n*-propyl tin dichloride, Cummins¹⁷ has assigned the higher frequency band at 580 cm^{-1} to Sn-C asymmetric stretching vibrations due to trans conformation and the one at 490 cm^{-1} to Sn-C asymmetric vibrations corresponding to gauche conformation of alkyl groups with respect to the tin. Tentative assignment of Sn-C frequencies in the various adducts on this basis, has been recorded in Table IV.

Sn-Cl frequencies : The Sn-Cl bond is considerably influenced by co-ordination. In order to maintain neutrality of the tin atom, even after it has accepted electron pairs from the ligands, the Sn-Cl bond is lengthened. This decreases the force constant and subsequently the frequency of the bond.

17. R. A. Cummins, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1965, **18**, 985.

TABLE IV

(Sn-C) frequencies
(cm^{-1})

	Asym.	Sym.
Pr_2SnCl_2	580 s, 490 m	—
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2$.Pyridine	580 m, 490 s	530 m
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2$. β -Picoline	580 m, 480 m	525 s
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2$. γ -Picoline	580 m, 490*s	530*s
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2$.Isoquinoline	570 s, 510 s	—
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2$.Piperdine	575 s	540 s
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot x$.Morpholine	580*S, 500 w	—
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2$.Aniline	585 w, 515*s	530 m
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot x$.Benzylamine	570*s, 490*w	—

* Possible ligand overlapping.

The infra red spectrum of solid di-*n*-propyl tin dichloride shows strong absorption at 320 cm^{-1} and 290 cm^{-1} and a weak peak at 305 cm^{-1} . They may be assigned to Sn-Cl vibrations. It is perhaps due to intermolecular halogen bonding that in the solid state spectra, the Sn-Cl vibrations are coming at 320 cm^{-1} , whereas it should have been somewhere around 350 cm^{-1} .³ The assignments of Sn-Cl frequencies in dipropyl tin dichloride and its adducts are given in the Table V.

TABLE V

(Sn-Cl) frequencies
(cm^{-1})

Pr_2SnCl_2	320 s, 305 w, 290 s.
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2$.Pyridine	300 m, 290 m, 280 m, 255 m.
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\beta$ -Picoline	300 w.
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\gamma$ -Picoline	300 m, 280 s.
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2$.Isoquinoline	300 m.
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2$.Piperidine	305 m, 295 m.sh, 255 w.
$\text{Pr}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot x$.Morpholine	370 m, 255 m.

Stereochemistry : 1 : 2 adducts of di-alkyl tin dihalides are known to possess octahedral configuration¹ and Sn-C and Sn-Hal. frequencies have been immensely helpful in deciding the structure. The presence or absence of Sn-C and Sn-Cl symmetric stretching vibrations has been very well utilized in locating the cis or trans positions of these two groups.

When the two halogens or alkyl groups are present in cis positions, due to non linear geometry, both the asymmetric and symmetric frequencies are expected to be infra red active whereas in a linear arrangement, symmetric stretching vibrations do not involve any change in dipole moment and hence are infra red inactive.

Absence of frequencies, corresponding to symmetric stretching vibrations of certain groups in the infra red spectra does indicate a linear arrangement and hence trans positions

of these groups. However, even in the trans position, if there is some distortion, the arrangement becomes nonlinear and the symmetric vibration becomes infra red active and thus appears in the spectra^{18,19}. Analogy with established structures in such cases is quite helpful.

In the adducts of di-*n*-propyl tin dichloride, the two *n*-propyl groups as well as the chlorines may exist either in cis or trans positions. Multiplicity of infra red frequencies corresponding to Sn-Cl vibrations and presence of infra red active Sn-C symmetric stretching vibrations suggest a non linear arrangement for the alkyl groups and also for the chlorines in the molecule.

Symmetric stretching frequencies for Sn-C in the spectra of the adducts of pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline, piperidine and aniline suggest that the adducts may have any one of the structures proposed below.

In these adducts the Sn-Cl frequencies have shown multiplicity which suggests that the two chlorines probably exist in the cis form, thus ruling out structure (C).

Again in case of the adducts $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{-Pyridine}$ and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{-Pyridine}$ although the Sn-C symmetric stretching vibrations are infra red active, the X-ray studies¹⁹ have shown that the alkyl groups are present in trans positions. The appearance of infra red absorption frequencies corresponding to Sn-C symmetric stretching vibrations has been accounted for by assuming a distortion in the C-Sn-C arrangement and thus making it nonlinear even in the trans positions of the alkyl groups.

In view of the above analogy it appears that the alkyl groups have preference for trans positions and structure (A) thus may be the only possibility.

Absence of the Sn-C symmetric frequency in isoquinoline adduct suggests a linear geometry for C-Sn-C with the two alkyl groups in the trans positions without any distortion in the octahedral arrangement as shown below.

In case of adducts with morpholine and benzylamine, no stoichiometry has been established analytically. However, if they are also assumed to have hexa co-ordinated tin,

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19. T. Tanaka, Y. Matsumura, R. Okawara, Y. Musya and S. Kinumaki, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1968, **41**, 1497.

they are likely to have the above structure because no frequency in their infra red spectra could be assigned to Sn-C symmetric stretching vibration.

Molar Conductivities : The molar conductance values in nitrobenzene of these adducts are in the region 2-4 cm² ohm⁻¹ mole⁻¹, which does not indicate the existence of free ions in the solution (Table I).

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